

A study of Process Optimization of Additive Manufacturing Process of AlSi10Mg-A Review

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ABSTRACT

Metal Additive Manufacturing (AM) processes, such as selective laser melting (SLM), enable the fabrication of arbitrary 3D-structures with unprecedented degrees of freedom. Research is rapidly progressing in this field, with promising results opening up a range of possible applications across both scientific and industrial sectors. Many sectors are now benefiting from fabricating complex structures using AM technologies to achieve the objectives of light-weighting, increased functionality, and part number reduction, among others. AM also lends potential in fulfilling demands for reducing the cost and design-to-manufacture time. Aluminum alloys are of the main material systems receiving attention in SLM research, being favored in many high value applications. Additive Manufacturing (AM) has become popular and substantial to manufacture direct functional parts in varieties industrial applications even in very challenging like aerospace, medical and manufacturing sectors. In the review, an AlSi10Mg alloy produced using selective laser melting (SLM), along with the implementation of an additional SLM process simulation. The efficacy and functionality of the additively manufactured (AM) components are contingent upon the chosen build orientation. By considering the provided process parameters.

Keywords: Selective Laser Melting (SLM), AlSi10Mg alloy, Wear Characterization, Hardness, Microstructure.

1. Introduction

Additive layer manufacturing has been utilized for more than three decades and is now commonly employed across various materials. There are numerous types of production machines available today, all of which share the common characteristic of creating three-dimensional shapes through the combination of multiple 2D slices. In recent years, additive manufacturing (AM) has been adapted for the rapid prototyping of metal components using methods such as direct laser manufacturing (DLM), electron beam melting (EBM), and selective laser melting (SLM). The AlSi10Mg alloy, along with Al-based and traditional casting alloys, is experiencing high demand in aerospace and automotive applications due to its low thermal expansion, lightweight nature, and exceptional mechanical properties. Moreover, the AlSi10Mg alloy has demonstrated great suitability for environments requiring 3D printed samples for scientific analysis. This alloy offers a compelling blend of attributes including high thermal conductivity, excellent weldability, corrosion resistance, and adequate hardenability. Additive manufacturing, when compared to conventional techniques, presents distinct advantages such as the rapid production of intricate custom structures with high resolution and minimal material wastage. Selective laser melting (SLM) represents a recently developed additive technology centered on laser powder bed fusion (LPBF). Utilizing a sliced CAD model, intricate freeform metal components are generated through a layer-by-layer process of laser scanning.

The AlSi10Mg alloy exhibits favorable weld ability attributed to the eutectic composition of Aluminum and Silicon. The rise in metal additive layer manufacturing (MALM) technology, particularly the innovative LPBF technology, is being explored by scholars and industry experts to determine the most suitable AM process for newly designed or existing CAD-based metal materials.

Optimization of SLM process parameters is essential to achieve the highest quality of fabricated metal components, characterized by flawless surfaces and full density. The refined technology not only leads to cost savings and streamlines the manufacturing process but also provides greater design flexibility. This research delves into the wear characterization of pin-on-disc tests, focusing on process optimization and the mechanical properties (hardness and density) of SLM-AlSi10Mg alloys. Among the key parameters in pin-on-disc testing, load (N), sliding speed (rpm), and duration (minutes) were identified as crucial inputs for wear assessment. This approach facilitates swift identification of optimized processing conditions to enhance wear resistance in SLM-AlSi10Mg components.

2.Literature survey

Optimization of the process parameters for 3D printing and additive manufacturing using AlSi10Mg alloy is crucial to attain superior quality, functionality, and reliability of printed components. AlSi10Mg, an aluminum-silicon-magnesium alloy, is extensively employed in additive manufacturing due to its advantageous blend of characteristics, such as high strength-to-weight ratio, good corrosion resistance, and exceptional thermal conductivity. To fully exploit the potential of this alloy in additive manufacturing, precise calibration and adjustment of various process parameters are indispensable. The thickness of each layer is a fundamental parameter that affects the resolution and surface quality of printed objects. Thinner layers generally lead to finer details and smoother surfaces, albeit with an increase in printing time. Striking a balance between layer thickness and printing efficiency is vital to fulfill specific design criteria. The laser power is a critical factor in determining the energy input during the printing process. The correct laser power setting ensures adequate melting and bonding of the powder layers. While higher laser power can accelerate printing speed, it also raises the risk of defects such as porosity. Hence, identifying the optimal laser power level tailored to the material properties and desired part characteristics is essential. The scanning speed, which dictates how quickly the laser moves across the powder bed, directly impacts the dwell time and heat input. Higher scanning speeds may speed up printing but could compromise part quality due to insufficient energy input. Conversely, slower speeds facilitate more thorough melting and bonding, thereby enhancing part integrity. The hatch distance, which is the distance between adjacent laser scan paths, is crucial for ensuring uniform melting and bonding while minimizing thermal stress and distortion. Optimization of the hatch distance involves striking a balance between adequate overlap and efficient material utilization. Regulating the temperature of the build platform is crucial for maintaining a stable printing environment and enhancing layer adhesion. Proper temperature control helps address issues like warping, distortion, and residual stresses, ensuring dimensional accuracy and part integrity. The quality of the powder feedstock significantly impacts printing outcomes. Characteristics such as particle size distribution, morphology, and chemical composition of the powder must be meticulously assessed to guarantee optimal flowability, laser absorption, and melt pool dynamics. Using high-quality powder is essential to achieve consistent and defect-free printed components.

The gas atmosphere within the build chamber, typically inert or nitrogen, plays a critical role in preventing oxidation and preserving material integrity, particularly for reactive materials like aluminum alloys. Maintaining a controlled gas environment enhances printing reliability and part quality. Post-processing parameters like heat treatment, stress relieving, and surface finishing techniques can further enhance the mechanical properties, surface finish, and dimensional accuracy of printed AlSi10Mg components. These steps are often necessary to meet specific performance criteria and improve the overall quality of the printed parts[1-5].

3.Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of process parameters

Selective Laser Melting (SLM) is a cutting-edge additive manufacturing technology that is revolutionizing the production of metal parts. SLM is a powder bed fusion process where a high-energy laser selectively melts and fuses metal powder particles layer by layer to create complex, customized parts. [1-2]. SLM offers several key advantages over traditional manufacturing methods. It enables the production of parts with intricate geometries that would be difficult or impossible to achieve through conventional techniques. SLM also allows for a high degree of customization, making it well-suited for applications that require personalized or bespoke components. [3-4]. One of the primary benefits of SLM is its ability to create parts with high accuracy and precision. The laser can melt the metal powder with micron-level precision, resulting in parts with excellent dimensional tolerances and surface finishes. This makes SLM an attractive option for industries that require tight manufacturing specifications, such as aerospace, medical, and automotive. However, SLM also presents some unique challenges, particularly when working with materials like aluminum and its alloys. Aluminum is highly reflective to the laser wavelengths typically used in SLM, which can reduce the amount of energy absorbed by the powder. This can lead to issues such as incomplete melting, porosity, and the formation of detrimental oxide layers. To overcome these challenges, researchers have explored strategies like using higher laser powers, optimizing scan speeds, and developing specialized powder compositions. Despite these challenges, SLM is poised to play a significant role in the emerging Industry 5.0 paradigm, which emphasizes the integration of customizable, sustainable, and human-centric technologies. SLM's ability to produce parts on-demand, reduce material waste, and enable the creation of complex, ergonomic designs aligns well with the goals of Industry 5.0. In conclusion, Selective Laser Melting is a powerful additive manufacturing technology that offers numerous advantages, including the ability to create complex, customized metal parts with high accuracy and precision. While there are still some technical hurdles to overcome, particularly with certain materials like aluminum, the continued development and optimization of SLM processes will likely make it an increasingly important tool in the manufacturing landscape of the future [5-8].

The factor that effects process parameter or Laser power, scan speed, hatch space, layer thickness and scan strategy. The Laser power manages the quantity of energy supplied to the substrate. Depending on the material, sufficient laser power is used for the complete melting of the powder particles as partial melting leads to defects upon solidification due to insufficient filling of the melt pool space. Equivalently, scanning speed regulates the solidification and melting rates. The hatch space determines the overlapping of adjacent tracks in a layer which allows them to bond together by metallurgical bonding. Layer thickness defines the thickness of powder distributed in a single layer. Larger layer thickness leads to incomplete melting and defects [9-12], such as balling. To determine the combined

impact of these variables, a parameter defined as volumetric energy density (Joule/mm^3), the most often form of energy density used by the researchers, is expressed as,

$$E = P / v * h * t \quad (1)$$

Where P is the laser power (W), v is the scanning speed (mm/s), t is the layer thickness (mm) and h is the hatch space (mm). Each Process Parameter Laser related, scan related, powder related and Temperature related has a substantial impact on the densification and mechanical characteristics of the AlSi10Mg final products fabricated by the SLM process which will be discussed individually in the following section [13-15].

3.2 Density

The density of a sample has a prominent effect on its mechanical-chemical properties. SLM alloy with high-density exhibits better tensile properties, impact energy, and reduced microstructure pores. Therefore, a better understanding of factors affecting relative density is essential. Effect of varying process parameters such as laser power, scan speed, hatch space, powder size, scanning strategy, chamber gas, etc., on the density values of SLM-AlSi10Mg, Relative density for AlSi10Mg is calculated through.

$$\text{Relative density} = \rho_{\text{sample}} / \rho_{\text{AlSi10Mg}} \quad (2)$$

Where ρ_{sample} is the measured density of the AlSi10Mg sample and ρ_{AlSi10Mg} is the density of base material which is $2.67 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$ for AlSi10Mg. The relative density of SLM AlSi10Mg manufactured by independently varying processing. The nature of relative density at varying laser power, hatch space and layer thickness. Laser power more or less than 250 W yielded comparatively decreased relative density due to lack of fusion pores at low laser power and at high laser power due to gas trapped pores. Similarly, at 0.13 mm hatch space, maximum relative density was noticed. depicts the value of relative density at different scan speeds. Constant relative density in the range of 1200 mm/s to 2000 mm/s, further increasing or decreasing the scan speed yielded lower relative density. All these parameters affect the energy density as shown in Equation (2). The selection of process parameters plays an important role in achieving desired properties with less defects. The low energy density is not sufficient to completely melt the powders which leads to partial melting of powder particles. Partial melting results in more porosity and reduce the relative density of the built part. However, other side, keyhole formation defects occur due to turbulence, spatter and pores formations in molten pools at the high energy density. The formation of these defect leads to decrease in the relative density of AM built part. The selection of optimum energy density is crucial for building additively manufactured parts with high relative density. The optimum range of energy density where samples produced the highest relative density was $32 \text{ J}/\text{mm}^3$ to $54 \text{ J}/\text{mm}^3$ [16-20].

4. Conclusion

In this study, experiments were performed to analyze the wear characteristics and frictional behavior of SLM- AlSi10Mg and as-cast Al6061 subjected to different loading conditions, varying sliding velocities, and durations of operation on a fixed wear track utilizing a pin-on-disc apparatus.

- Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies are revolutionizing industrial production by facilitating the efficient production of end components for utilization across diverse sectors such as aerospace, automotive, and healthcare. Among these techniques, Selective Laser Melting (SLM) stands out as the most auspicious.
- Prior research has indicated that components fabricated through SLM demonstrate superior tensile strength and hardness values in comparison to those manufactured using traditional casting methodologies. Nevertheless, deficiencies like partially melted powder, porosity due to gas entrapment, surface imperfections, loosely adhered particles, semi-welded structures, balling, and the staircase effect may contribute to the suboptimal longevity of the parts. It is crucial to appropriately optimize process parameters to yield high-quality finished components.
- The influence of key SLM process parameters such as laser power, hatch spacing, and scanning speed on mechanical properties has been extensively investigated. Additionally, the impact of scanning strategies, built orientation, and preheating of the substrate plate has also been scrutinized.

Reference

1. Ramin Rahmani, Javad Karimi, Pedro R. Resende, João C. C. Abrantes and Sérgio I. Lopes Overview of Selective Laser Melting for Industry 5.0: Toward Customizable, Sustainable, and Human-Centric Technologies May 2023.
2. Gor M, Soni H, Wankhede V, Sahlot P, Grzelak K, Szachgluchowicz I, et al. A critical review on effect of process parameters on mechanical and microstructural properties of powder-bed fusion additive manufacturing of ss316l.
3. Materials (Basel) 2021;14:1e29. [https://doi.org/ 10.3390/ma14216527](https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14216527). 3.Sufiiarov VS, Popovich AA, Borisov EV, Polozov IA, Masaylo DV, Orlov AV. The effect of layer thickness at selective laser melting. Procedia Eng 2017;174:126e34.
4. Gor M, Soni H, Wankhede V, Sahlot P, Grzelak K, Szachgluchowicz I, et al. A critical review on effect of process parameters on mechanical and microstructural properties of powder-bed fusion additive manufacturing of ss316l. Materials (Basel) 2021;14:1e29. [https://doi.org/ 10.3390/ma14216527](https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14216527).

5. Hyer H, Zhou L, Park S, Gottsfritz G, Benson G, Tolentino B, et al. Understanding the laser powder bed fusion of AlSi10Mg alloy. *Metallogr Microstruct Anal* 2020;9:484e502. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13632-020-00659-w>.
6. Sabzi HE, Rivera-Dí'az-del-Castillo PEJ. Defect prevention in selective laser melting components: compositional and process effects. *Materials (Basel)* 2019;12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12223791>.
7. Gor M, Dobriyal A, Wankhede V, Sahlot P, Grzelak K, Kluczynski J, et al. Density prediction in powder bed fusion additive manufacturing: machine learning-based techniques. *Appl Sci* 2022;12:7271. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12147271>.
8. Hirata T, Kimura T, Nakamoto T. Effects of hot isostatic pressing and internal porosity on the performance of selective laser melted AlSi10Mg alloys. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2020;772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2019.138713>.
9. Raus AA, Wahab MS, Shayfull Z, Kamarudin K, Ibrahim M. The influence of selective laser melting parameters on density and mechanical properties of AlSi10Mg. *MATEC Web Conf* 2016;78:1e9. <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/20167801078>.
10. Mfusi BJ, Tshabalala LC, Popoola API, Mathe NR. The effect of selective laser melting build orientation on the mechanical properties of AlSi10Mg parts. *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng* 2018;430:0e7. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/430/1/012028>.
11. Awd M, Stern F, Kampmann A, Kotzem D, Tenkamp J, Walther F. Microstructural characterization of the anisotropy and cyclic deformation behavior of selective laser melted AlSi10Mg structures. *Metals (Basel)* 2018;8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met8100825>.
12. Gouveia RM, Silva FJG, Atzeni E, Sormaz D, Alves JL, Pereira AB. Effect of scan strategies and use of support structures on surface quality and hardness of L-PBF AlSi10Mg parts. *Materials (Basel)* 2020;13:2248. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13102248>.
13. Liu B, Li BQ, Li Z. Selective laser remelting of an additive layer manufacturing process on AlSi10Mg. *Results Phys* 2019;12:982e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2018.12.018>.
14. Yu WH, Sing SL, Tian XL, Chua CK. Effects of re-melting strategies on densification behavior and mechanical properties of selective laser melting ALSI10MG parts. *Proc Int Conf Prog Addit Manuf May*, 2018;2018:476e81. <https://doi.org/10.25341/D48309>.

15. Balbaa MA, Ghasemi A, Fereiduni E, Elbestawi MA, Jadhav SD, Kruth JP. Role of powder particle size on laser powder bed fusion processability of AlSi10Mg alloy. *Addit Manuf* 2021;37:101630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2020.101630>.
16. Rakesh CHS, Priyanka N, Jayaganthan R, Vasa NJ. Effect of build atmosphere on the mechanical properties of AlSi10Mg produced by selective laser melting. *Mater Today Proc* 2018;5:17231e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2018.04.133>.
17. Yusuf SM, Hoegden M, Gao N. Effect of sample orientation on the microstructure and microhardness of additively manufactured AlSi10Mg processed by high-pressure torsion. *Int J Adv Manuf Technol* 2020;106:4321e37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-019-04817-5>.
18. Aboulkhair NT, Everitt NM, Ashcroft I, Tuck C. Reducing porosity in AlSi10Mg parts processed by selective laser melting. *Addit Manuf* 2014;1:77e86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2014.08.001>.
19. Thijs L, Kempen K, Kruth JP, Van Humbeeck J. Finestructured aluminium products with controllable texture by selective laser melting of pre-alloyed AlSi10Mg powder. *Acta Mater* 2013;61:1809e19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2012.11.052>.
20. Weingarten C, Buchbinder D, Pirch N, Meiners W, Wissenbach K, Poprawe R. Formation and reduction of hydrogen porosity during selective laser melting of AlSi10Mg. *J Mater Process Technol* 2015;221:112e20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2015.02.013>.
21. Matjeke VJ, Moopanar C, Bolokang AS, van der Merwe JW. Effect of heat treatment time on the microstructure and mechanical deformation behavior of additivemanufactured AlSi10Mg components. *Prog Addit Manuf* 2020;5:379e85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40964-020-00139-1>.